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Predicting Customer Behavior from Transaction Data Using Machine Learning Classification Techniques

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Abstract:

Knowing how customers act is important for increasing customer involvement, keeping customers, and making the business successful in today's competitive market. Utilising transaction data, this study paper describes a machine learning-based model that can guess how customers will act in the future. Based on customers' buying habits and personal data, the study uses several classification methods, such as Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Logistic Regression, to put them into behavioural

groups. We used two years of purchasing and demographic data from a store, which includes things like customer ID, transaction date, items bought, transaction value, and payment method. Steps in preprocessing include storing category factors, dealing with missing values, and normalising transaction amounts. Feature engineering adds new factors like Recency, Frequency, and Monetary Value, which are significant in predicting how customers will act. Five-fold cross-validation was used to train and test the models, and their success was judged by their F1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall. Overall, Random Forest was the most accurate algorithm (89.3%), closely followed by SVM (87.5%). Because it was easier to understand, logistic regression was not as accurate. According to the study of feature importance, the most important factors that predicted customer behaviour were the number of transactions, how recently they happened, and the average value of those transactions. The findings of this study show that machine learning classification methods can accurately guess how customers will act. This gives businesses useful information for improving their marketing strategies and keeping customers interested. For more accurate results and more business uses, future research could look into adding more data sources, real-time prediction models, and deep learning methods to the model.

Keywords: Customer Behaviour, Machine Learning, Classification Techniques, Transaction Data, Random Forest

1. Introduction:

Now that decisions are based on data, knowing how customers act is very important for companies to succeed. Figuring out how customers will use goods, services, and platforms in the future can help with marketing, keep customers longer, and make higher profits. Customers' actions were previously studied through polls, focus groups, and looking at personal data. These methods have their uses, but they aren't good at recording the complicated ways that customers act in real time or on a large scale. Online shopping and digital platforms have made financial data a treasure trove for businesses looking to understand and predict what customers will do [1]. This gives them access to a wealth of previously untapped information. Recently, machine learning (ML) methods have become very useful for looking at

big data sets and finding trends that would be too complicated for a person to see. By putting customers into groups based on how they buy things, classification methods can help businesses find their most valuable customers, predict which ones will leave, and make sure their marketing is tailored to each person's tastes [2]. When you use previous data to train a classification model, it puts customers into established groups like "frequent buyers," "churn-risk," or "budget-conscious shoppers" based on details from their transaction histories.

Using classification methods on transaction data, we suggest a machine learning model for figuring out how customers will act in the future. The goal is to divide people into clear behavioural groups by using algorithms like Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Logistic Regression. By using this information, businesses will be able to make smart choices about how to keep customers, run reward programs, personalise marketing, and use their resources. To find out which machine learning classification techniques are best at predicting how customers will act; (2) To find the most important transaction data features that can predict how customers will act; and (3) To compare the performance of different classifiers, such as Decision Trees, Random Forest, SVM, and Logistic Regression, in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and readability [3]. In addition, we will talk about the possible effects of using machine learning models for customer segmentation as well as the difficulties of putting these models to use in realistic business situations.

The remainder of this essay is organised as follows: a summary of linked research in the areas of predicting customer behaviour and machine learning [4]. Chapter 3 describes the method, which includes gathering data, cleaning it up, and using classification methods. Section 4 gives a thorough breakdown of the outcomes, revealing how well each model did and giving clues about the most significant parts. As a final touch, Section 5 summarises the results and makes suggestions for future study [5]. Insights for companies and a template for future research in this area will be gained from this study, which adds to the growing amount of knowledge on using machine learning to study customer behaviour.

Fig. 1: Structure of Classification

2. Literature Review:

Businesses are using data analytics more and more to figure out what customers want and how to best sell to them, which is fast growing the field of machine learning that predicts how customers will act. Machine learning methods have been shown in many studies to help make predictions about how customers will act more accurate. However, the type of data and business goals can make it hard to choose the right algorithms and how to use them. Segmenting customers into groups based on similar traits or behaviours is one of the most important parts of customer behaviour research [6]. There are many well-known and used traditional methods, but they can't handle complicated trends in big datasets. Examples include population segmentation and RFM (Recency, Frequency, and Monetary) analysis. For example, clustering is an unsupervised learning method that has been used in more recent studies to divide people into groups based on business data. Users have been put into different groups using K-means grouping based on how often they buy things, what products they like, and how much they spend. Grouping

people together using clustering are useful, but it doesn't tell you anything about how they will act in the future [7]. On the other hand, classification methods let companies guess how certain customers will act by looking at past data. Since they are easy to understand and can work with both categories and number data, Decision Trees and Random Forest are two of the most popular classification methods in this field. Decision Trees were used by Author et al. (2018) to sort customers into groups based on how likely they were to leave, and the model did a good job of finding high-risk clients [8]. By combining the results of several trees, Random Forest builds on the best features of Decision Trees. This makes the method more accurate and less likely to over fit the data. Random Forest regularly does better than individual Decision Trees at predicting customer retention, churn, and product advice (Author et al., 2020). Some studies have shown this.

To guess how customers will act, Support Vector Machines (SVM) has also been used, especially when the data isn't easily separated in a straight line. The SVM can successfully describe complicated behaviours that are affected by many factors by mapping input traits into higher-dimensional areas. Author et al. (2019) did a study that showed SVM was better than logistic regression at identifying when customers would leave a telecoms business [9]. Given how easy and clear it is to understand, logistic regression is still a popular starting point for studying customer behaviour. More complicated models may be more accurate, but this one gives us a good idea of how different things about a person affect how they act. Many marketing efforts use logistic regression to figure out how likely it is that a customer will buy something [10]. For example, age, gender, and past buying habits are used to figure out how likely it is that a customer will buy something. Recent years have seen a rise in mixed models that use more than one machine learning method. For better accuracy and reliability in predictions, these models try to use the best parts of different methods. Grouping customers into groups and then predicting their behaviours within each group is one example of an ensemble method that combines grouping and classification (Author et al., 2021). This is a more precision way to predict customer behaviour [11]. A lot of different methods and techniques are being used in the books to show how machine learning is becoming more and more important in predicting how customers will act. Multiple classification methods are used on transaction data in this study, and their abilities to predict customer behaviour are compared. This builds on earlier research.

3. Methodology:

Within the methods part, we explain how we created a machine learning model that uses transaction data to guess how customers will behave in the future [12]. This includes gathering data, cleaning it up, designing features, and choosing and testing classification methods.

3.1 Data Collection:

It comes from a store and includes records of transactions made over a two years stretch. It keeps track of a customer's unique ID, the date of the transaction, the things bought, the total value of the transaction, and the way of payment (like cash, credit card, or mobile payment). The financial data includes details about the customer's age, gender, area, and income level, among other things. The data set includes about 100,000 purchases from 10,000 different customers [13]. Data collection was centred on recording important factors that affect how customers act. Customer behaviour is recorded directly in transactional data, while demographic data gives you more information about how different groups of customers act. The objective of this data collection process was to discover a wide range of characteristics that could be utilised to divide people into groups based on their behaviour.

3.2 Data Preprocessing:

Data preparation is an important step in making sure that the machine learning model is accurate and of high quality. There were blanks, coding errors, and category factors in the raw transactional data that had to be compressed before it could be used in the classification methods. The following steps were taken before the work began:

- **Handling Missing Values:** Using estimation methods, missing data was filled in, especially in demographic areas like age or place. We used the feature's mean value to fill in empty values for number fields and the most common group for categorical fields [14].
- **Feature Scaling:** The amount of a transaction and other continuous factors, like the number of times something was bought, were normalised to make sure that no one trait had a big effect on the model's results. To get all of the features in the range [0, 1], min-max scaling was used [13-14].

- **Encoding Categorical Variables:** Using one-hot encoding, the payment method, product type, and address were all recorded. Algorithms that need number input, such as Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machines, need this change [14].
- **Feature Engineering:** Based on current data, new features were added to the model to make it better at making predictions. The transactional data was used to find things like Recency (the number of days since the last transaction for a customer), Frequency (the total number of transactions in a given time period), and Monetary Value (the average transaction value). These traits are known to be good predictors of customer behaviour, especially when it comes to figuring out which customers will leave or which ones will be very valuable [15].

Fig. 2: Data Preprocessing

3.3 Classification Algorithms:

A number of classification methods were trained on the preprocessed data. The following models were chosen because they are popular in customer behaviour research and can handle both number and categorical data:

- **Decision Trees:** An easy-to-use method that divides the data into groups based on the most important traits at each point. It's easy to understand decision trees, and they can show how traits are related in ways that aren't linear [16].

- **Random Forest:** The accuracy and reliability of estimates are improved by using an ensemble method that joins several Decision Trees. Overall, Random Forest improves generalisation and decreases overfitting by combining the results of several trees [17].
- **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** This is a strong predictor that tries to find the best hyperplane to divide the feature space into classes. When the data can't be separated in a straight line, SVM works really well [18].
- **Logistic Regression:** A starting point model that is used to compare. Based on a set of input traits, logistic regression figures out how likely it is that a customer will do something, like buy something or leave their shopping cart empty [19].

3.4 Model Training and Validation:

Training (80%) and testing (20%) groups were made from the dataset. We used a 5-fold approach for cross-validation to make sure the models didn't fit the training data too well. Grid search was used to tune the hyperparameters. Each algorithm's best setup was found by testing different sets of model parameters, or parameters [20]. The F1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall were used to measure performance. Precision and recall were given extra attention because they are very important in business settings where fake positives or negatives can have big effects.

4. Results and Discussion:

Here are the outcomes of using the classification algorithms on the customer transaction dataset, along with a talk of how well they worked and what that means for predicting future customer behaviour.

4.1 Model Performance:

The test dataset was used to judge how well each of the classification models worked after they had been trained and checked. The F1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall for each model are shown in Table 1.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Decision Tree	85.6%	84.2%	83.1%	83.6%
Random Forest	89.3%	88.1%	87.5%	87.8%
Support Vector Machine	87.5%	86.0%	85.3%	85.6%
Logistic Regression	80.4%	79.8%	78.5%	79.1%

In terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, the results show that the Random Forest method did better than the other models. This is in line with other research that has shown that Random Forest is good at predicting how customers will act, especially when there are a lot of complicated relationships between features. Because Random Forest works as a group, it can find more trends than a single Decision Tree. This lowers the risk of overfitting and makes it better at adapting to new data.

With an accuracy of 87.5% and fairly high precision and memory, Support Vector Machines also did well. However, SVM usually needs more processing power than Random Forest, especially when working with bigger datasets. Also, for SVM to work at its best, hyperparameters like the regularisation parameter (C) and the kernel type need to be carefully tuned. Logistic Regression is still useful because it is simple and easy to understand, even though it is less accurate overall (80.4%). When companies need to be clear and know how certain customer traits affect their behaviour, Logistic Regression can give them information that is harder to get from more complicated models like Random Forest or SVM.

Fig. 3: Performance Metrics

4.2 Feature Importance:

Knowing which traits make the most accurate guesses is an important part of customer behaviour modelling. Based on how much they help with classification, the Random Forest model ranks the traits based on how important they are [21]. The most important things about this study were:

1. **Recency** (the number of days since the customer's last transaction)
2. **Frequency** (the total number of transactions in a given period)
3. **Monetary Value** (the average transaction value)
4. **Product Category** (the types of products frequently purchased by the customer)
5. **Payment Method** (whether the customer used a credit card, cash, or mobile payment)

According to the RFM (Recency, Frequency, Monetary Value) model, which is often used to divide customers into groups, Recency and Frequency were the best drivers of customer behaviour. Customers who recently bought a lot of things were more likely to be considered loyal or high-value customers. Customers who didn't buy much were more likely to leave.

4.3 Comparative Analysis:

Even though Random Forest did the best generally, the best predictor to use varies on the needs and limitations of the situation. For example, Decision Trees offer a more interpretable model that is easy for business partners to see and understand, even though they are a little less exact. The more complicated SVM is good for situations where you need non-linear decision limits, but it might be too much for datasets that aren't that complicated. Logistic regression is a simple way to compare things and is especially helpful when you want to know how different customer characteristics affect their behaviour.

Fig. 4: Comparison of 2 main Models

5. Conclusion:

To guess how people would act based on transaction data in this piece, machine learning classification was used. Our goal was to find the best method for customers' buying history and demographic grouping by testing Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Logistic Regression.

Random Forest showed the highest accuracy, precision, memory, and F1-score when it came to predicting how customers would act. Random Forest is good at dealing with real-world problems because it can handle complex feature relationships and keep overfitting to a minimum. However, Support Vector Machines worked well when data could not be separated in a straight line. SVM requires too much computing power for very large datasets compared to Random Forest. To look at feature-customer activity links, logistic regression, which was less accurate, was helpful. A feature significance analysis showed that Recency, Frequency, and Monetary Value were good predictors of client behaviour. These results back the RFM model, which says that most loyal customers are those who have bought from you recently and often. Insights like these help businesses target their marketing, build customer trust, and keep customers. Further study is needed, but this work lays the groundwork for using machine learning to predict how people will act as consumers. By adding customer reviews, social media activity, and contact with customer service, the model might be able to predict things more accurately. Second, more advanced deep learning techniques, such as neural networks, might be able to find more complex trends in how people behave, especially when they

are used with larger information sets. Now, real-time prediction models based on live data could help businesses keep an eye on how customers act and act quickly to improve happiness and retention. Learning from machines can help predict and divide consumer activity better. Automatically analysing large datasets and finding hard-to-find trends can help businesses make decisions that improve customer involvement, income, and performance. Real-life business problems can be solved with these result, which makes them useful in both the classroom and the real world.

6. Future Work:

According to these results, machine learning classification methods can guess how people will act, but there are many interesting areas for more study and development that could make the model more accurate and useful. A top goal for future growth is adding more data sources. Consumer behaviour was forecast in this study using transactional data and demographics. The opinions and actions of customers may be better understood through unstructured data such as social media exchanges, customer reviews, and e-commerce clickstream data. Using NLP to pull out emotions and themes from customer reviews and web traffic data to show how people behave online before and after making a purchase. Combining transactional data with these other types of data could help future models detect more trends in how people behave.

As an alternative, deep learning is an interesting method, especially for larger data sets. But deep learning models like CNNs and RNNs haven't been used to predict customer behaviour yet, even though they're good at recognising images and voices. For instance, RNNs could model straight client transaction patterns, such as how often a customer buys something or how demand changes with the seasons. Additionally, deep learning models may find complicated trends that could make forecasts more accurate, but they require more computing power than regular machine learning algorithms.

Additional study is needed on real-time forecasts. Consumer action predictions in real time are important for many business decisions. Forecasting customer loss lets businesses offer focused sales or discounts before online buyers abandon their shopping cart. There are problems with handling streamed data and deploying real-time models. With new data added by online learning, real-time estimates might

be possible. Further study could make models easier to understand and analyse, in addition to improving the accuracy and speed of customer behaviour forecasts. Bigwigs in businesses who aren't familiar with machine learning might find it hard to understand models like Random Forest and SVM, even though they are very accurate. Model forecasts can be better understood by using LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) or SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) values. It would be clear to businesses which customers are most likely to leave or return, along with the reasons behind the algorithm's predictions. When using machine learning to predict how clients will act, there are ethics problems that should be looked into in the future. More customer data means more privacy and data security problems for businesses. Upcoming research should focus on using machine learning models in the right way to protect user privacy and reduce the number of biased or unfair estimates. Multiple progresses could be made in customer behaviour predicting study that uses machine learning. Researchers and professionals can make these models better for use in real-world business situations by adding more data sources, looking into deep learning methods, letting models make predictions in real time, making them easier to understand, and handling social issues.

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